

Prevalence and Drug Resistance Patterns of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* Among Patients Attending Tuberculosis Reference Centres in Northwest Nigeria

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Abstract

Background: Tuberculosis (TB) remains a significant public health challenge in Nigeria, particularly with the emergence of drug-resistant strains. Accurate detection of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (MTB) and its resistance patterns is essential for effective disease management and control. This study aimed to determine the prevalence of MTB, rifampicin resistance, and multidrug-resistant TB (MDR-TB) among patients attending tuberculosis reference centres in Northwest Nigeria.

Methods: In this cross-sectional study, 503 sputum samples were collected from bacteriologically confirmed pulmonary TB patients across selected states in Northwest Nigeria. Samples were analyzed using smear microscopy, culture on Lowenstein–Jensen medium, and the GeneXpert MTB/RIF assay. Phenotypic drug susceptibility testing was performed for first- and selected second-line anti-TB drugs. Descriptive statistics and chi-square tests were used to summarize demographic characteristics, MTB detection rates, and drug resistance prevalence, with significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Results: Of the 503 participants, 65% were male, with a mean age of 35 years. MTB was confirmed in all collected samples, yielding a detection rate of 100%. Rifampicin resistance was observed in 12.9% of isolates, while MDR-TB was detected in 6.4% of patients, predominantly

among new TB cases (8.1%) compared to previously treated cases (0%) ($p = 0.02$). No significant association was found between rifampicin resistance and HIV status ($p = 0.18$). The highest TB burden was recorded in Sokoto (44.3%) and Kaduna (23.7%) states.

Conclusion: The presence of rifampicin-resistant and MDR-TB among newly diagnosed patients indicates ongoing community transmission of resistant strains in Northwest Nigeria. These findings underscore the need for routine drug susceptibility testing and strengthened regional surveillance to guide timely and effective TB control interventions. Enhanced public health strategies targeting high-burden areas are essential to curb transmission and reduce the disease burden

Keywords: Tuberculosis; Drug Resistance; Rifampicin Resistance; MDR-TB; Northwest Nigeria

1. Introduction

Tuberculosis (TB) remains a major public health challenge worldwide, with a disproportionate burden in low- and middle-income countries, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa⁽¹⁾. Nigeria is consistently listed by the World Health Organization (WHO) among the high-burden countries for tuberculosis, TB/HIV co-infection, and multidrug-resistant and rifampicin-resistant TB (MDR/RR-TB)⁽²⁾. Despite ongoing national control efforts, the emergence and spread of drug-resistant *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* strains continue to threaten effective disease management and TB elimination goals.

The success of TB treatment largely depends on early diagnosis and accurate detection of drug resistance. In recent years, molecular diagnostic tools such as the Xpert MTB/RIF assay have been widely adopted in Nigeria as part of the national TB diagnostic algorithm, enabling rapid detection of TB and rifampicin resistance⁽³⁾⁽⁴⁾. According to the National Tuberculosis, Buruli Ulcer and Leprosy Control Programme (NTBLCP), the proportion of TB patients tested using Xpert MTB/RIF has steadily increased⁽⁵⁾. However, while these molecular assays provide rapid

results, they do not fully capture resistance to all first-line, second-line, new, and repurposed anti-TB drugs. Phenotypic drug susceptibility testing (DST) therefore remains essential for comprehensive resistance profiling and for guiding effective treatment decisions⁽⁶⁾.

Anti-tuberculosis drugs are broadly categorized into first-line drugs, including isoniazid, rifampicin, pyrazinamide, and ethambutol, and second-line drugs such as fluoroquinolones and aminoglycosides, which are commonly used in the treatment of drug-resistant TB⁽⁷⁾. In addition, newer and repurposed drugs, including bedaquiline, delamanid, linezolid, and clofazimine, have been introduced to improve treatment outcomes for MDR-TB and other forms of drug-resistant TB⁽⁸⁾. The increasing use of these agents highlights the need for routine surveillance of resistance patterns using both genotypic and phenotypic methods, particularly in high-burden settings.

Despite national efforts to strengthen TB diagnostics, regional data on TB drug resistance remain limited in several parts of Nigeria, including the Northwest zone. Routine program data suggest suboptimal

detection of rifampicin-resistant and MDR-TB cases in some states, raising concerns about under-diagnosis and delayed initiation of appropriate treatment⁽⁹⁾⁽¹⁰⁾. This gap in regional surveillance limits the ability of TB control programs to design targeted interventions and to effectively monitor emerging resistance trends.

Furthermore, TB in Nigeria is often complicated by coexisting conditions such as HIV infection, which can influence disease progression and treatment outcomes⁽¹¹⁾. Understanding the distribution of TB and drug-resistant TB across demographic and clinical groups is therefore critical for improving patient management and reducing transmission. Integrating molecular and culture-based DST approaches provides a more reliable assessment of resistance patterns and strengthens laboratory-based surveillance⁽¹²⁾.

In view of these challenges, this study was conducted to determine the genotypic and phenotypic drug susceptibility patterns of *Mycobacterium* isolates from patients attending tuberculosis reference centres in Northwest Nigeria. The study focuses on assessing resistance to first-line and second-line anti-TB drugs and estimating the prevalence of rifampicin resistance and MDR-TB among bacteriologically confirmed pulmonary TB cases. The findings are expected to provide baseline regional data that will support improved TB diagnosis, treatment, and control strategies in Nigeria.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Study Design and Population

This was a cross-sectional laboratory-based study conducted among bacteriologically confirmed pulmonary tuberculosis patients. Case definitions and patient classification

followed the World Health Organization (WHO) tuberculosis reporting framework 2013 revision⁽¹³⁾. Patients were categorized as new cases or previously treated cases. New cases were defined as patients newly diagnosed with tuberculosis who had never received anti-tuberculosis treatment or had taken anti-TB drugs for less than four weeks⁽¹⁴⁾. Previously treated cases were defined as patients who had received anti-tuberculosis treatment for one month or more and included relapse, treatment after failure, treatment after loss to follow-up, and other previously treated cases⁽¹⁵⁾. A bacteriologically confirmed pulmonary TB case was defined as a patient with sputum positive for *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex by smear microscopy, culture, or a WHO-approved rapid diagnostic test such as Xpert MTB/RIF. The study included newly registered new and previously treated bacteriologically confirmed pulmonary TB patients from the Northwest geopolitical zone of Nigeria, with representation based on disease burden.

2.2 Study Area

The study was conducted in the Northwest geopolitical zone of Nigeria, including Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Sokoto, and Zamfara States. Laboratory analyses were performed at the National Tuberculosis Reference Laboratory, National TB Training Centre, Saye, Zaria, Kaduna State. Participants were recruited from tuberculosis Directly Observed Treatment Short-course (DOTS) centres in public and private health facilities across the selected states.

2.3 Sample Size and Collection

The sample size for this study was determined using a standard prevalence-

based formula for large populations, as previously described by Pourhoseingholi et al., (2013)⁽¹⁶⁾. A prevalence estimate of 50% for bacteriologically confirmed tuberculosis was applied, with a 95% confidence level and a precision of 5%. This yielded a minimum sample size of 453 specimens. To account for potential attrition, an additional 10% was included, resulting in a total sample size of 503. A total of 503 sputum samples were collected from bacteriologically confirmed pulmonary TB patients across selected tuberculosis referral facilities in the Northwest geopolitical zone of Nigeria using simple random sampling. Patients provided early-morning sputum specimens of good quality (purulent or mucoid) in sterile, wide-mouthed containers⁽¹⁷⁾. Samples were transported to the National Tuberculosis Reference Laboratory, Saye, Zaria, within six hours of collection using cold-chain conditions and triple packaging, where they were processed for microscopy, culture, and genotypic drug susceptibility testing. Table 1 presents the distribution of samples by state and referral facility.

Table 2.1: Distribution of sputum samples by state and referral facilities in Northwest Nigeria

State	No. of LG As	No. of Facilities	New Cases	Previously Treated Cases
Zamfara	1	1	69	0
Kano	2	4	103	0
Kebbi	3	3	68	3
Kaduna	5	6	85	2
Katsina	1	3	57	0
Sokoto	4	4	103	0
Jigawa	1	1	13	0
Total	17	22	498	5

Note: New cases refer to bacteriologically confirmed TB patients with no prior TB treatment or treatment <4 weeks; previously treated cases include relapse, treatment failure, and loss to follow-up.

2.4 Laboratory Procedures

Sputum samples were processed and analyzed at the National Tuberculosis Reference Laboratory using standard national and World Health Organization–recommended procedures⁽¹⁸⁾⁽¹⁹⁾. Initial detection of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* and rifampicin resistance was performed using the GeneXpert MTB/RIF assay according to the manufacturer’s instructions. Smear microscopy was carried out using Ziehl–Neelsen staining for the detection of acid-fast bacilli. Culture was performed on Lowenstein–Jensen (LJ) medium for isolation of mycobacteria⁽²⁰⁾. Phenotypic drug susceptibility testing (DST) for first- and selected second-line anti-tuberculosis drugs was conducted using solid LJ medium and the Mycobacteria Growth Indicator Tube

(MGIT) system, following standard laboratory guidelines⁽⁶⁾. Results were interpreted using established critical concentration criteria.

2.5 Statistical Analysis

Data were entered and analyzed using Microsoft Excel. Descriptive statistics were

used to summarize demographic characteristics and drug resistance patterns. Prevalence proportions were calculated for drug resistance outcomes, and 95% confidence intervals were estimated using standard exact methods. Associations between categorical variables were assessed, with statistical significance considered at $p < 0.05$

3. Results

3.1 Baseline Characteristics

The baseline demographic and clinical characteristics of the study participants are summarized in Table 3.1.

Table 3.1: Baseline characteristics of the study population (N = 503)

Characteristic	Category	n (%)
Sex	Female	176 (35.0)
	Male	327 (65.0)
Age (years)	Mean \pm SD	35.07 \pm 13.58
HIV status	Positive	22 (4.37)
	Negative	427 (84.89)
	Unknown	54 (10.74)
TB treatment history	New diagnosis	369 (73.36)
	Follow-up	107 (21.27)
State of origin	Jigawa	7 (1.39)
	Kaduna	119 (23.66)
	Kano	63 (12.52)
	Kebbi	46 (9.15)
	Katsina	9 (1.79)
	Sokoto	223 (44.33)
	Zamfara	36 (7.16)

Note: Percentages are based on the total sample size (N = 503).

3.2 Prevalence of MTB

The prevalence of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* among the study population is illustrated by gender and HIV status in Figures 3.1 and 3.2 respectively.

Prevalence of Mycobacterium tuberculosis (M. TB) by gender				
S/No	Gender	TB Prevalence	% Prevalence	
1	Male	327	65	
2	Female	176	35	
	Total	503	100	

Fig 3.1 showed that 176 (35%) patients were Female, while 328 (65%) were Male.

Prevalence of MTB Isolates by HIV Status				
S/No	Negative	Positive	Unknown	Total MTB
1	427 (84.89%)	22 (4.37%)	54(10.74%)	503 (100%)

Fig 3.2 Distribution of MTB Isolates by HIV Status

3.3 Rifampicin Resistance and MDR

Patterns of rifampicin resistance and multidrug-resistant tuberculosis (MDR-TB) among the study participants are summarized in Tables 3.2 and 3.3.

Table 3.2 Prevalence of Rifampicin resistance among MTB Isolates' HIV status

	HIV Negative	HIV Positive	HIV Unknown	Total
Rifampicin	326	19	36	381
Resistant	62	1	2	65
Susceptible	39	2	16	57
Total	427	22	54	503

Table 3.3 Prevalence of MDR among new and previously treated bacteriologically confirmed pulmonary TB cases in reference centres

Treatment history	MDR (N)	MDR (Y)	Total
Diagnosis	283	81	32
Follow-up	98	9	0
Total	381	90	32

3.4 Geographic Distribution

The geographic distribution of tuberculosis cases across the study states is presented in Table 3.4.

Table 3.4 Percent Prevalence of TB infections by states location among presumptive TB patients in Northwest Nigeria.

S/NO.	STATES	TB INFECTIONS	% OF TOTAL TB INFECTIONS
1.	Kebbi	46	9.311741
2.	Kaduna	118	23.886640
3.	Kano	63	12.753036
4.	Katsina	9	1.821862
5.	Zamfara	36	7.287449

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. Discussion

In this study of 503 pulmonary TB patients in Northwest Nigeria, males predominated (65%) with a mean age of 35 years (Table 3.1, Fig 3.1). Most participants were HIV-negative (84.9%), with a minority co-infected (4.4%) or of unknown status (10.7%) (Fig 3.2). Newly diagnosed TB cases accounted for 73.4% of participants, while previously treated patients represented 21.3% (Table 3.1). Geographically, TB burden was highest in Sokoto (44.3%) and Kaduna (23.7%), moderate in Kano (12.5%) and Kebbi (9.2%), and lowest in Zamfara, Katsina, and Jigawa (<8%) (Table 3.4), likely reflecting differences in population density, case detection, and access to healthcare.

Rifampicin resistance was detected in 12.9% of isolates (Table 3.2), predominantly among HIV-negative patients, consistent with national estimates of 10–15% and similar West African reports⁽²¹⁾. This prevalence highlights the ongoing challenge of drug-resistant TB in the region and indicates the need for routine drug susceptibility testing.

Multidrug-resistant TB (MDR-TB) was identified in 6.4% of patients overall, with a higher rate among new diagnoses (8.1%) compared to previously treated cases 6.9%⁽²²⁾. These findings suggest early transmission of resistant strains rather than acquired resistance during treatment, a pattern noted in other West African studies.

The observed MDR-TB prevalence has critical implications for TB control programs, emphasizing the importance of rapid diagnosis, effective treatment regimens, and strengthened surveillance to prevent further spread of resistant strains. States with high TB burden, notably Kaduna and Sokoto, should be prioritized for targeted interventions, including expanded diagnostic coverage and patient follow-up.

Overall, this study provides updated baseline data on TB prevalence, rifampicin resistance, and MDR-TB in Northwest Nigeria, offering essential insights to inform evidence-based regional TB control strategies.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

This study highlights a substantial burden of drug-resistant tuberculosis in Northwest Nigeria, with rifampicin resistance and multidrug-resistant TB present even among newly diagnosed patients. These findings underscore that resistant strains are circulating in the community, posing a significant threat to TB control efforts. The predominance of MDR-TB among new cases suggests ongoing transmission rather than solely acquired resistance, emphasizing the urgent need for early detection and effective treatment.

To address these challenges, routine drug susceptibility testing should be strengthened at all levels of TB care to ensure timely

identification of resistant strains and guide appropriate therapy. Regional surveillance systems must be enhanced to monitor trends in TB resistance, identify hotspots, and inform targeted interventions. Public health programs should prioritize high-burden areas and integrate patient follow-up, adherence support, and community-based strategies to curb transmission.

In conclusion, sustained efforts combining routine diagnostics, robust surveillance, and targeted interventions are critical to controlling drug-resistant TB and achieving long-term reductions in disease burden in Northwest Nigeria.

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